

ASSESSMENT OF REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND DYNAMICS OF MUNICIPALITIES WITH A POPULATION FROM 10,000 TO 30,000 IN EASTERN BULGARIA**Slaveva Kr.,***Assoc. Prof., Ph.D. in Statistics**Statistics Department**Economic Academy – Svishtov, Bulgaria***Petrov K.,***Prof., Ph.D. in Geography**Regional Development Department**UNWE, Sofia, Bulgaria***Tsonkov N.***Regional Development Department**Assoc. Prof., Ph.D. in Economics**UNWE, Sofia, Bulgaria***Abstract**

The article examines the dynamics of municipalities with a population between 10 and 30 thousand people in Eastern Bulgaria. Most of the analysis focuses on the existing disparities in the country. The study fills a deficit related to the territorial disparities analysis in a specific part of the national territory of Bulgaria. The object of the study is medium-sized municipalities in Eastern Bulgaria (1-30 thousand people). The main research objective is to analyze the regional disparities between these municipalities in Eastern Bulgaria. The authors use statistical estimation methods such as regression, and correlation analysis. They are combined with territorial approaches and a descriptive method. The research results show significant regional differences among the municipalities considered. The development potential of the municipalities increases with the proximity of the municipalities to the Black Sea coast. This is a way to overcome regional disparities.

Keywords: regional development, regional disparities, Eastern Bulgaria, municipalities.

Introduction

Eastern Bulgaria is a spatial area that includes the NUTS II planning regions of North-East (14,487 km²) and South-East (19,799 km²) and covers an area of 34 286 km². Important economic areas related to regional development such as the districts of Stara Zagora, Sliven, Yambol, Shumen, Targovishte, and the Black Sea districts of Burgas, Varna, and Dobrich are concentrated in this part of Bulgaria. Thus, geo-economically, a region is formed which is an intersection point of economic, trade, transport, energy, geostrategic, and political importance. In this most southeastern part of the EU, European policies are concerned with challenging the planning capacity of the regions, seeking a new regional development model, encouraging investment, and providing more security because this is effectively an external border of the EU.

To a large extent, Eastern Bulgaria can be divided into Black Sea territories and continental territories (non-Black Sea), allowing us to consider two parallel regional development processes. These are the state and development of the Black Sea municipalities and others of the hinterland with a population of 10 to 30 thousand people. In this situation, we cannot miss the leaders of the region, which are the cities of Varna and Burgas, which have an important strategic importance not only for Bulgaria but also have the potential to be regional economic centers of significance for the whole European area. The new economic profile creation in the context of transformation is one of the opportunities to examine to what extent these municipalities have managed to restructure themselves given their depressive state since the early 1990s.

The objectives of reducing and limiting economic, social, and demographic disparities must be the guiding principles of contemporary regional policy. The setting of regional objectives should be based on scientifically sound analyses and proposals, the implementation of which should be a priority for the state and their implementation should be financially assured. In-depth study of the situation and the results achieved in economic, social, and demographic aspects in the regions, identifying the degree of disparity between the districts forming the territories and the municipalities within them. Drawing up regional profiles of districts and regions based on a system including key economic, social, and demographic indicators, we study the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and obstacles to development, which are a reliable basis for forming a vision not only for the municipality development. As a result of these analyses, it is quite logical and justified to highlight the objectives and the necessary measures to achieve them, which should become an important part of the strategic documents at regional and national levels.

Research Methodology

The study focuses on two planning regions North East and South East planning regions, the subject of the study is the municipalities with populations from 10,000 to 30,000 people in them, the study period is 2018-2020 and is based on official statistics from NSI.

In the study, the authors develop a regional disparities assessment model using a set of approaches and methods - territorial, geographic, systems approach, causal analysis, and statistical method (regression and correlation analysis).

Analysis of scientific literature

The analysis of the existing studies shows that none focus specifically on the eastern part of the Bulgarian state. Most studies look at all regions of Bulgaria. Some of them analyze regional differences in the context of the effectiveness of the regional policy [1, p. 1-5, 2, p. 86-99, 3, p. 55-62, 4, p. 53-66]. In such studies, we are not able to reveal the differences in detail because the analysis would be too extensive. In this sense, the authors focus on the specific regions of research in Bulgaria, which can then be compared with other European territories. The analysis of the scientific literature reveals several similarities regarding the challenges and problems existing in the Bulgarian regions [5, p. 44-54, 6, p. 28, 7, p. 49-67, 8, p. 27-39, 9, p. 53-66]. The authors consider the significance of the studies that compare economic and social indicators of Bulgaria and other European countries. Such studies show the great differences that exist not only in Bulgaria between different regions, but also compared to countries such as Switzerland, Romania, and other European countries [10, p. 91-121, 11, p. 32-36].

To reveal, assess, and compare regional differences between municipalities in Eastern Bulgaria, it is

necessary to find statistically significant correlations. This implies a proper collection of economic and social information processing [12, p. 521-529, 13, p. 32]. When combining statistical and spatial research, we use a variety of statistical and mathematical models, which in turn require the search for various statistical dependencies and modeling [14, p. 219-249, 15, p. 39-63, 16].

Analysis of key indicators for the Northeast and Southeast regions

One of the key objectives of this study is to establish the regional GDP structure and the contribution of individual regions. This is an important aspect of the study, as it allows for the regional development assessment and the identification of the underlying reasons for observed differences in regional development. For the period under study, the South West region dominated the regional GDP structure, accounting for between 48% and 51%, while the contribution of the other GDP generation regions was much smaller - South Central with a relative share of about 14% South East with 10-12%, North East about 10%, North Central and North West with a share of about 7% (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Regional GDP structure of Bulgaria 2018-2020

Source: NSI and authors' calculations.

The intensity of changes in the structure of GDP and gross value added by statistical region is measured by the integral coefficient of structural change (K_s), which takes range values of 0 to 1 - the closer the value is to 0, the less pronounced the changes, and the closer the value is to 1, the more pronounced the structural changes. The calculated integral coefficients of structural changes and differences concerning the regional GDP structure of the previous year show that in 2019 there are small changes $K_s=0,03055$ and in 2020 compared to 2019 there are extremely weak or almost no changes - $K_s=0,01295$. The results show that there is a persistent regional GDP structure that is not uniform and the reason for this is the different degree of economic development of the planning regions in the country.

To a significant extent, the peculiarities of the economic development of the regions are expressed in the production structure represented by the main sectors -

agricultural, industry, and services. The services sector is dominant in Bulgaria and accounts for about 70% of the gross value added for the period 2018-2020, but it is also dominant in the North-Eastern region with about 66-67%, and in the South-Eastern region between 54% and 60% (Table 1). Comparing the sectoral structure of the two regions with the sectoral structure of the country by year showed that the differences are much smaller for the Northeast region, for which the following values of the integral coefficient of structural change and differences were obtained - $K_{s2018} = 0.04089$, $K_{s2019} = 0.04092$, $K_{s2020} = 0.05318$, while for the Southeastern region, the differences in structure are more pronounced, being the largest for 2018 - $K_{s2018} = 0.21983$. The differences in sectoral structure gradually decrease and the coefficients are $K_{s2019} = 0.151786$ and $K_{s2020} = 0.09322$, respectively in the following years.

Table 1

Sectoral structure of gross value added for the period 2018-2020

Sectors	Gross added value structure								
	North East Region			South East Region			Bulgaria		
	2018	2019	2020	2018	2019	2020	2018	2019	2020
Agriculture	6,0	6,2	6,4	4,8	5,1	5,7	3,9	3,7	4,0
Industry	27,1	26,1	27,4	41,0	37,3	34,3	25,8	25,0	25,3
Services	66,9	67,8	66,2	54,1	57,6	60,0	70,3	71,2	70,7

Source: NSI and authors' calculations.

Tracking the changes in the sectoral structure of the GAV gives grounds to claim that significant changes in the structure do not occur, but they do occur and they are more pronounced for the South East region - $K_{s2019/2018} = 0.05274$ and $K_{s2020/2019} = 0.039303$ compared to the values of the integral coefficient for the North East region - $K_{s2019/2018} = 0.01336$ and $K_{s2020/2019} = 0.020934$. At the same time, tracking the dynamics of the relative shares of individual districts in the formation of GDP for their respective regions provides rich analytical information. The obtained results highlight the leading role of the Varna district in the formation of GDP of the North-Eastern region - the relative share is between 60% and 63%, while the districts of Dobrich and Shumen account for about 14% and Targovishte about 10%. Two districts in the Southeast region stand out as determining in GDP formation - Stara Zagora district with a share of 40.7% in 2020 and Burgas district with a share of 36.8% in 2020, while Sliven district accounts for 12.7% in 2020 and Yambol district for 9.8%. There are no significant changes in the intra-regional structure by districts and this conclusion is confirmed by the values of the integral coefficients - for the Northeast region $K_{s2019/2018} = 0.00577$ and $K_{s2020/2019} = 0.02077$ and the Southeast region confirmed by the values of the

integral coefficients - for the Northeast region $K_{s2019/2018} = 0.045934$ and $K_{s2020/2019} = 0.065107$.

By comparing the indicator "GDP per capita" it can be established what processes are taking place - convergence or deepening of disparities between the regions, the comparison is about the North-Eastern and South-Eastern regions and the indicator for Bulgaria. The data visualization in Figure 2 clearly shows that the GDP per capita indicator is significantly lower for the two regions analyzed compared to the country indicator - for the North East it is lower by 3,109 BGN for 2018, 3,861 BGN for 2019, and 4,189 BGN for 2020, and for the South East it is lower by 2828 BGN for 2018, 4199 BGN for 2019 and 5122 BGN for 2020. The conclusion is that regional differences and disparities are increasing - the indicator for the North East for 2018 is 19.9% lower than the national average and in the following years the differences are widening and it is already lower by 22.5% for 2019 and 24.2% for 2020 respectively, and for the South-East region the widening gaps are even more pronounced, as GDP per capita is lower by 18.1% for 2018, 24.5% for 2019 and 29.6% for 2020. Therefore, the gap between the Northeast and the Southeast according to the indicator "GDP per capita" is widening and instead of convergence, there is an intensification of regional disparities and disparities.

Figure 2 GDP per capita 2018-2020

Source. NSI.

Comparative analysis of key economic indicators for municipalities with a population of 10,000 to 30,000 in the North-East and South-East regions

The analysis is based on official statistical data from the NSI for 21 municipalities with a population of 10,000 to 30,000 people in the Northeast and Southeast regions (2018-2020). The available information allows us to examine the differences between these municipalities in the following indicators: number of enterprises,

output, net sales, accommodation, foreign direct investment, and average gross wage.

The indicators dynamics are examined for the municipality and overall, highlighting trends in their evolution. The measurement and assessment of the degree of variation in the main economic indicators for the municipalities studied was carried out using the standard

deviation (σ) and the coefficient of variation ($V\sigma$). Using regression and correlation analysis, dependencies between the indicators under study were established.

The number of non-financial enterprises in the analyzed municipalities for 2018 is 18866 pcs. and they represent 16.9% of the enterprises in the Northeast and Southeast regions and 4.6% of the enterprises in the country, for 2019 they are 19078 pcs. or 16.8% of the enterprises for the two regions and 4.55% of the enterprises in the country, and for 2020 their number is 18609 pcs. respectively 17.1% and 4.5%. The number of enterprises in the municipalities increased by 212 pcs or 1.12% in 2019 compared to 2018, but in 2020 the number of enterprises decreased by 469 pcs or 2.46%. The largest number of enterprises is in the municipality of Kazanlak, followed by the municipalities of Pomorie, Aitos, Balchik, and Nova Zagora, and the smallest number of enterprises is in the municipality of Tvarditsa. In 2019, the number of enterprises in Kazanlak Municipality increased by 111 pcs (3.44%), in Pomorie Municipality by 56 pcs (2.88%), Dolni Chiflik Municipality by 32 pcs (6.07%), Aksakovo Municipality by 27 pcs (3.51%), Veliki Preslav Municipality by 18 pcs (4.59%), etc. (Table 2). In 2020, for almost all municipalities, a decrease in the number of enterprises was

found, the most pronounced being for Pomorie municipality - a decrease of 203 pcs. or 10.13%, for Balchik municipality by 78 pcs. or 6.07%, for Kazanlak municipality a decrease of 55 pcs. or 1.65%, etc., the main reason for this being the start of the Covid-19 pandemic and the measures and restrictions imposed, which create additional difficulties in the functioning of enterprises. In 2020, a significant increase in the number of enterprises registered for the municipality of Aksakovo by 21 pcs. or by 2.63%, the main reason for the increase is the proximity to the town of Aksakovo. The principal factor driving the expansion of Aksakovo is the proliferation of businesses in the area. This is largely attributable to the growth of Varna, which has created a conducive environment for entrepreneurial activity.

The analysis of the degree of the dispersion according to the number of non-financial enterprises in the surveyed municipalities, using the standard deviation (σ) and the coefficient of variation ($V\sigma$), shows an increase in dispersion, which means that the existing disparities are widening - for 2018 $\sigma = 674,7$ bp. and $V_\sigma = 72,1\%$, for 2019 $\sigma = 668,5$ bp. and $V_\sigma = 73,6\%$, for 2020 $\sigma = 644,2$ bp. and $V_\sigma = 72,7\%$. The results show that the variation in the number of non-financial enterprises is large.

Table 2

Dynamics of the number of enterprises by municipality for the period 2018-2020

Municipalities	Enterprises number			Absolute growth (numer)		Growth rate (%)	
	2018	2019	2020	$\Delta_{2019/2018}$	$\Delta_{2020/2019}$	$T'_{2019/2018}$	$T'_{2020/2019}$
Aksakovo	770	797	818	27	21	3,51	2,63
Dolni Chiflik	527	559	543	32	-16	6,07	-2,86
Provadia	721	716	688	-5	-28	-0,69	-3,91
Balchik	1313	1286	1208	-27	-78	-2,06	-6,07
Kavarna	815	789	775	-26	-14	-3,19	-1,77
Tervel	464	446	446	-18	0	-3,88	0,00
Omurtag	521	529	527	8	-2	1,54	-0,38
Popovo	875	884	885	9	1	1,03	0,11
Veliki Preslav	392	410	408	18	-2	4,59	-0,49
Novi Pazar	596	597	561	1	-36	0,17	-6,03
Aitos	1370	1365	1369	-5	4	-0,36	0,29
Karnobat	944	947	944	3	-3	0,32	-0,32
Pomorie	1947	2003	1800	56	-203	2,88	-10,13
Ruen	629	629	632	0	3	0,00	0,48
Nova Zagora	1201	1209	1187	8	-22	0,67	-1,82
Tvurditza	329	338	335	9	-3	2,74	-0,89
Kazanlak	3228	3339	3284	111	-55	3,44	-1,65
Radnevo	586	583	581	-3	-2	-0,51	-0,34
Chirpan	600	600	601	0	1	0,00	0,17
Elhovo	681	684	648	3	-36	0,44	-5,26
Stralja	357	368	369	11	1	3,08	0,27

Source: NSI and authors' calculations.

Based on the analysis of the number of non-financial enterprises as an indicator of entrepreneurial activity and the results obtained from it, the municipalities are divided into the following 4 groups:

- Low entrepreneurial activity, which includes municipalities with up to 500 non-financial enterprises;
- Moderate entrepreneurial activity, which includes municipalities with more than 500 to 1000 non-financial enterprises;

- Significant entrepreneurial activity, which includes municipalities with more than 1000 to 1500 non-financial enterprises;

- High entrepreneurial activity, which includes municipalities with more than 1500 non-financial enterprises.

Table 3

Distribution of municipalities according to the number of non-financial enterprises

Degree	Nonfinancial enterprises number	Municipalities
Low	Up to 500	Tvurditza, Stralja, Veliki Preslav Tervel
Moderate	From 500 to 1000	Omurtag, Dolni Chiflik, Novi Pazar, Radnevo, Chirpan, Ruen, Elhovo, Provadia, Kavarna, Aksakovo, Popovo, Karnobat
Significant	From 1000 to 1500	Nova Zagora, Balchik, Aitos
High	over 1500	Pomorie, Kazanlak

Source: NSI and author's calculations.

The output produced by the enterprises in the surveyed municipalities of North East and South East regions for the year 2018 is 7129248000 BGN for the year 2019 is 7270689000 BGN and for the year 2020 is 6346735000 BGN, the increase for the year 2019 is 141441000 BGN or by 1.98% but for the year 2020, it registers a decline of 923954000 BGN or by 12.71 and

is a direct result of the Covid-19 pandemic. A significant increase in the value of production volume for 2019 was found for the municipalities of Radnevo, Aksakovo, Pomorie, Aytos, Dolni Chiflik, Omurtag, etc. Based on the data in Table 4, it is found that for 2020 a decrease is reported for the majority of municipalities, which is strongly pronounced for the municipalities of Radnevo, Balchik, Kazanlak, and Pomorie.

Table 4

Production dynamics by municipalities for the period 2018-2020.

Municipalities	Produced products (thousands in Bulgarian currency)			Absolut growth (thousands in Bulgarian currency)		Growth rate (%)	
	2018	2019	2020	$\Delta_{2019/2018}$	$\Delta_{2020/2019}$	$T'_{2019/2018}$	$T'_{2020/2019}$
Aksakovo	582603	662421	656998	79818	-5423	13,7	-0,8
Dolni Chiflik	50221	61749	62428	11528	679	23,0	1,1
Provadia	128805	124627	113638	-4178	-10989	-3,2	-8,8
Balchik	478062	482033	336127	3971	-145906	0,8	-30,3
Kavarna	325302	266688	244280	-58614	-22408	-18,0	-8,4
Tervel	86270	80699	67222	-5571	-13477	-6,5	-16,7
Omurtag	98993	111271	112859	12278	1588	12,4	1,4
Popovo	311526	317441	327192	5915	9751	1,9	3,1
Veliki Preslav	99664	105311	92716	5647	-12595	5,7	-12,0
Novi Pazar	153201	149161	144651	-4040	-4510	-2,6	-3,0
Aitos	112678	126959	124112	14281	-2847	12,7	-2,2
Karnobat	588837	595216	530396	6379	-64820	1,1	-10,9
Pomorie	222368	245959	192311	23591	-53648	10,6	-21,8
Ruen	258884	234119	197422	-24765	-36697	-9,6	-15,7
Nova Zagora	439942	421262	386328	-18680	-34934	-4,2	-8,3
Tvurditza	34171	30808	31536	-3363	728	-9,8	2,4
Kazanlak	1384327	1360596	1299932	-23731	-60664	-1,7	-4,5
Radnevo	1404487	1537743	1100298	133256	-437445	9,5	-28,4
Chirpan	150304	156424	154776	6120	-1648	4,1	-1,1
Elhovo	99071	77340	68214	-21731	-9126	-21,9	-11,8
Stralja	119532	122862	103299	3330	-19563	2,8	-15,9

Source: NSI and author's calculations.

The analysis of the degree of divergence according to the output volume has shown that the differences existing so far are very pronounced and deepening - for 2018 $\sigma = 379639$ thousand BGN and $V_{\sigma} = 111,8\%$, for 2019 $\sigma = 397784,6$ thousand BGN and $V_{\sigma} =$

114,9%, for 2020 $\sigma = 332342,5$ thousand BGN and $V_{\sigma} = 109,9\%$. The analysis results show that the Output-produced indicator variation is large.

Table 5

Distribution of municipalities by output

Degree	Produced Production (thousands in Bulgarian currency)	Municipalities
Low	Up to 100 000	Tvurditza, Dolni Chiflik, Tervel, Elhovo, Veliki Preslav
Moderate	From 100 000 to 200 000	Omurtag, Stralja, Provadia, Aitos, Novi Pazar, Chirpan
Significant	From 200 000 to 1000 000	Ruen, Pomorie, Kavarna, Popovo, Nova Zagora, Balchik, Karnobat, Aksakovo
High	over 1 000 000	Kazanlak, Radnevo

Source: NSI and authors' calculations.

For the period 2018-2020 the net sales revenue in the surveyed municipalities of the North-East and South-East regions for 2018 is BGN 8796249 thousand, for 2019 is BGN 9006646 thousand and for 2020 is BGN 8256526 thousand, the increase for 2019 is BGN 210397 thousand or by 2.39%, but also for this indicator there is a decrease by BGN 750120 thousand or by 8.33% for 2020, A significant increase in net sales revenue

for 2019 was found for the municipalities of Aksakovo, Kazanlak, Radnevo and Karnobat, while a significant decrease was registered for the municipalities of Kavarna, Balchik, and Ruen (Table 6). Net sales revenues declined for almost all of the research municipalities. The municipalities with the highest rate of decline were Balchik, Radnevo, Pomorie, Kavarna, Karnobat, and Elhovo, where the effects of the pandemic on tourism and industry are visible.

Table 6

Dynamics of net sales revenues by municipality for the period 2018-2020.

Municipalities	Net sales revenue (thousands in Bulgarian currency)			Absolute growth (thousands in Bulgarian currency)		Growth rate (%)	
	2018	2019	2020	$\Delta_{2019/2018}$	$\Delta_{2020/2019}$	$T'_{2019/2018}$	$T'_{2020/2019}$
Aksakovo	669887	778402	738783	108515	-39619	16,20	-5,09
Dolni Chiflik	95662	105248	107865	9586	2617	10,02	2,49
Provadia	181357	180902	165509	-455	-15393	-0,25	-8,51
Balchik	597957	570733	442099	-27224	-128634	-4,55	-22,54
Kavarna	374428	299565	249559	-74863	-50006	-19,99	-16,69
Tervel	104499	101212	91925	-3287	-9287	-3,15	-9,18
Omurtag	140646	159971	177897	19325	17926	13,74	11,21
Popovo	781813	813573	896705	31760	83132	4,06	10,22
Veliki Preslav	120562	120173	120440	-389	267	-0,32	0,22
Novi Pazar	187789	191491	185499	3702	-5992	1,97	-3,13
Aitos	196221	220793	207735	24572	-13058	12,52	-5,91
Karnobat	683667	714939	614761	31272	-100178	4,57	-14,01
Pomorie	299505	315549	252730	16044	-62819	5,36	-19,91
Ruen	280579	254043	222469	-26536	-31574	-9,46	-12,43
Nova Zagora	539502	544580	500753	5078	-43827	0,94	-8,05
Tvurditza	48978	49846	49011	868	-835	1,77	-1,68
Kazanlak	1594856	1645316	1662187	50460	16871	3,16	1,03
Radnevo	1406328	1442574	1111591	36246	-330983	2,58	-22,94
Chirpan	194303	193370	195445	-933	2075	-0,48	1,07
Elhovo	160475	155996	132935	-4479	-23061	-2,79	-14,78
Stralja	137235	148370	130628	11135	-17742	8,11	-11,96

Source: NSI and authors' calculations.

The assessment of the degree of divergence between municipalities according to net sales revenues shows that there are pronounced differences that are deepening - for 2018 BGN $\sigma = 412151,8$ thousand and $V_{\sigma} = 98,4\%$, for 2019 BGN $\sigma = 427955,6$ thousand and $V_{\sigma} = 99,8\%$, for 2020 BGN $\sigma = 399314,4$ thousand and $V_{\sigma} = 101,6\%$.

Once more, the municipalities of Kazanlak and Radnevo stand out, as they are home to several significant industrial enterprises. The municipalities are categorized into four groups according to their degree of economic development, with the lowest category representing those with the lowest net sales revenues. The municipalities of Tvurditsa and Tervel fall into the low economic development group according to all three indicators discussed in the research.

Table 7

Distribution of municipalities according to net sales revenues

Degree	Net sales revenue (thousands in Bulgarian currency)	Municipalities
Low	Up to 100,000	Tvurditza, Tervel
Moderate	From 100,000 to 200,000	Dolni Chiflik, Veliki Preslav, Stralja, Elhovo, Provadia, Omurtag, Novi Pazar, Chirpan
Significant	From 200,000 to 1000 000	Aitos, Ruen, Kavarna, Pomorie, Balchik, Nova Zagora, Karnobat, Aksakovo, Popovo
High	over 1 000 000	Radnevo, Kazanlak

Source: NSI and authors' calculations.

Investments especially foreign direct investments in non-financial enterprises are an important factor for economic development, production expansion and renewal, increasing economic activity and employment, reducing unemployment, etc. The dynamics of foreign direct investment in non-financial enterprises represent a significant indicator of economic activity and the economic development level of municipalities. For 2018-2020, the total foreign direct investment amount in non-financial enterprises in the surveyed municipalities in 2018 was 506,866 thousand euros. In 2019, there was a 5.93% decrease in foreign direct investment, amounting to 30067.8 thousand euros. Conversely, in 2020, there was a 6.78% increase in foreign direct investment, amounting to 32309.7 thousand euros. The undisputed leader in attracting foreign direct investment is the municipality of Kavarna - for 2018 in the amount of EUR 191,629.5 thousand, for 2019 - EUR 191,173 thousand, and 2020 - EUR 194,682.7 thousand (Tables 8 and 9). Kazanlak Municipality ranks second in attracting foreign direct investment with EUR 75481.1 thousand, EUR 87266.4 thousand, and EUR 107216.9 thousand, respectively, followed by Nova Zagora Municipality (EUR 69118.9 thousand, EUR 72758.5 thousand and EUR 68623.2 thousand). A lasting trend towards increasing foreign direct investment is characteristic of the municipality of Kazanlak - an increase for 2019 by EUR 11785.3 thousand (15.61%) and 2020 by EUR 19950.5 thousand (22.86%). Tracking the status and dynamics of foreign direct investments in the analyzed municipalities gives grounds to claim that their size in most municipalities can not become determinants of their development due to lack of interest from investors, insufficient presentation of the opportunities of

municipalities, poor condition of infrastructure and transport network, shortage of qualified workforce, etc. At the same time, in some municipalities there is also a process of outflow of foreign direct investments due to reasons of different nature, but similar to the reasons for the decrease of investor interest from abroad.

The degree of divergence between municipalities according to foreign direct investment in non-financial enterprises is very pronounced and deepening - for 2018 $\sigma = 46060$ thousand euro and $V_{\sigma} = 163,6\%$, for 2019 $\sigma = 47914,5$ thousand euro and $V_{\sigma} = 170,8\%$, for 2020 $\sigma = 29947,5$ thousand euro and $V_{\sigma} = 166,5\%$. The obtained measures of variation confirm the conclusions regarding the high degree of differences between municipalities according to the amount of foreign direct investment attracted.

Tourism plays a key role in the North East and South East development, accounting for 50% of the country's accommodation, around 70% of rooms and beds, almost 60% of overnight stays, and over 65% of overnight revenue between 2018 and 2020. The number of beds in accommodation in the municipalities covered by the study for 2018 is 38,484 and they represent 15.9% of the number of beds in accommodation in the North East and South East region and 11.5% of the number of beds in accommodation in the country, for 2019. In 2019, the number of beds in accommodation establishments in the Northeast and Southwest regions was 38,844 or 15.9% of all beds in accommodation establishments in the two regions and 11.4% for the country, 2020 The number of beds in accommodation establishments in the two observed regions and Bulgaria is 29,502 - 16% and 10.5% respectively.

Table 8

Dynamics of foreign direct investment in non-financial enterprises by the municipality for the period 2018-2020

Municipalities	Foreign direct investments (thousands in euros)			Absolute growth (thousands in euros)		Growth rate (%)	
	2018	2019	2020	$\Delta_{2019/2018}$	$\Delta_{2020/2019}$	$T'_{2019/2018}$	$T'_{2020/2019}$
Aksakovo	12619,5	11059,8	9233,4	-1559,7	-1826,4	-12,36	-16,51
Dolni Chiflik	-868,9	..	2648,1	-	-	-	-
Provadia	-25	-19,6	25,9	5,4	45,5	-21,60	-232,14
Balchik	41407,9	34319,4	38610,9	-7088,5	4291,5	-17,12	12,50
Kavarna	191629,5	189173	194682,7	-2456,5	5509,7	-1,28	2,91
Tervel	8253,7	-1648,9	4381,1	-9902,6	6030	-119,98	-365,70
Omurtag	..			-	-	-	-
Popovo	..			-	-	-	-
Veliki Preslav	398,8	772,9	734,1	374,1	-38,8	93,81	-5,02
Novi Pazar	25836,3	26229,4	23627,3	393,1	-2602,1	1,52	-9,92
Aitos	2600,8	-38,6	1960,7	-2639,4	1999,3	-101,48	-5179,53
Karnobat	36693,5	34844,1	37142,4	-1849,4	2298,3	-5,04	6,60
Pomorie	10987,5	-9536,9	-9410,6	-20524,4	126,3	-186,80	-1,32
Ruen	15448,1	17762	21162,7	2313,9	3400,7	14,98	19,15
Nova Zagora	69118,9	72758,5	68623,2	3639,6	-4135,3	5,27	-5,68
Tvurditza	-50,8	-	-	-	-
Kazanlak	75481,1	87266,4	107216,9	11785,3	19950,5	15,61	22,86
Radnevo	290,3	339	..	48,7	-	16,78	-
Chirpan	8051,6	7767	6676,6	-284,6	-1090,4	-3,53	-14,04
Elhovo	9127,6	5769,4	1833,3	-3358,2	-3936,1	-36,79	-68,22
Stralja	-134,4	-18,7	-40,8	115,7	-22,1	-86,09	118,18

Source: NSI and author's calculations.

Table 9

Distribution of municipalities according to foreign direct investment

Degree	Foreign direct investments (thousands in euros)	Municipalities
Low	Up to 1,000	Pomorie, Strqalja, Tvurditza, Provadia, Omurtag, Popovo, Radnevo, Dolni Chiflik, Veliki Preslav
Moderate	From 1 000 to 10 000	Aitos, Tervel, Elhovo, Chirpan
Significant	From 10 000 to 50 000	Aksakovo, Ruen, Novi Pazar, Karnobat, Balchik
High	Over 50 000	Nova Zagora, Kazanlak, Kavarna

Source: NSI and authors' calculations.

The number of beds in accommodation in 2019 compared to 2018 decreased by 360 or 7.6%. For the period 2018-2020, the largest number of accommodation places is in the municipality of Balchik, followed by the municipalities of Pomorie, Kavarna, and Dolni Chiflik - they account for 92% of the number of beds in accommodation places in the analyzed municipalities (Table 10). It is logical that the Black Sea municipalities, which have traditionally established themselves as preferred holiday destinations, have a developed tourist infrastructure, offer a wide variety of services and other amenities for tourists, and have a leading role in this indicator. In 2019 and 2020, the largest decrease in the number of beds in accommodation facilities compared to 2018 is registered for the municipality of Balchik - by 869 (3.21%) and 8405 (32.12%), respectively. The

largest increase in the number of beds in accommodation establishments was recorded in Pomorie municipality in 2019 compared to 2018 - their increase was by 36.76% or by 1408 pcs. In summary, the year 2020 is characterised by a reduction in the number of beds in accommodation facilities. This is largely attributable to the global pandemic of Covid-19 and the restrictive measures introduced to limit the spread of the virus. However, it is important to note that the tourism sector has been particularly affected by these developments. There are also opportunities for tourism development in other municipalities, albeit on a much smaller scale, which can develop as municipalities offering good opportunities for historical tourism, cultural tourism, wine tourism, rural tourism, etc. by promoting historical heritage, natural attractions, folklore, local and traditional products, organizing festivals, fairs, etc. events.

Table 10

Dynamics of the number of accommodation places by municipality for the period 2018-2020

Municipalities	Accommodation places (number)			Absolute growth (number)		Growth rate (%)	
	2018 г.	2019 г.	2020 г.	$\Delta_{2019/2018}$	$\Delta_{2020/2019}$	$T'_{2019/2018}$	$T'_{2020/2019}$
Aksakovo	60	60	40	0	-20	0,00	-33,33
Dolni Chiflik	2693	2455	2180	-238	-275	-8,84	-11,20
Provadia	145	168	171	23	3	15,86	1,79
Balchik	27039	26170	17765	-869	-8405	-3,21	-32,12
Kavarna	2545	2469	2293	-76	-176	-2,99	-7,13
Тервел	30	30	30	0	0	0,00	0,00
Omurtag	34	34	34	0	0	0,00	0,00
Popovo	38	85	28	47	-57	123,68	-67,06
Veliki Preslav	213	225	234	12	9	5,63	4,00
Novi Pazar	42	42	52	0	10	0,00	23,81
Aitos	84	76	70	-8	-6	-9,52	-7,89
Karnobat	157	163	158	6	-5	3,82	-3,07
Pomorie	3830	5238	4888	1408	-350	36,76	-6,68
Ruen	27	27	27	0	0	0,00	0,00
Nova Zagora	382	430	408	48	-22	12,57	-5,12
Tvurditza	26	39	39	13	0	50,00	0,00
Kazanlak	888	901	853	13	-48	1,46	-5,33
Radnevo	-	-	-	-	-	-	-!
Chirpan	98	79	79	-19	0	-19,39	0,00
Elhovo	117	117	117	0	0	0,00	0,00
Stralja	36	36	36	0	0	0,00	0,00

Source: NSI and authors' calculations.

The analysis of the degree of variation according to the number of beds in accommodation in the studied municipalities using the standard deviation (σ) and the coefficient of variation ($V\sigma$) shows an extremely large variation, which means that the existing differences between the studied municipalities are widening. The main reason is their geographical location and proximity to the Black Sea - for 2018 $\sigma = 297,7$ и $V\sigma =$

327,3%, 2019 $\sigma = 6126,6$ and $V\sigma = 315,4\%$, for 2020 $\sigma = 4191,3$ and $V\sigma = 284,7\%$. The results show that the variation in the number of beds in accommodation facilities is slightly decreasing, but still very large. This is visible in Table 11, which ranks the municipalities according to the number of beds in accommodation facilities - Balchik municipality stands out.

Table 11

Distribution of municipalities according to the number of beds in accommodation facilities

Degree	Bed number in accommodation places	Municipalities
Low	Up to 100	Radnevo, Ruen, Popovo, Tervel, Omurtag, Stralja, Tvurditza, Aksakovo, Novi Pazar, Aitos, Chirpan
Moderate	From 100 to 1,000	Elhovo, Karnobat, Provadia, Veliki Preslav, Nova Zagora, Kazanlak
Significant	from 1 000 to 5 000	Dolni Chiflik, Kavarna
High	over 5 000	Balchik, Pomorie

Source: NSI and authors' calculations.

A number of dependencies have been investigated between the presented main economic indicators for the municipalities by means of regression and correlation analysis, among which the dependencies between the number of enterprises and output, the number of enterprises and net sales revenue, output and net sales revenue have stood out.

The results of the analysis show that the relationship between the number of enterprises and output is significant, with a correlation coefficient of $r=0.5216$

and a coefficient of determination of $R^2 = 0,272$, implying that 27.2% of the output variation is due to variation in the number of enterprises, while 72.8% of the variation is due to other factors not included in the model. The regression coefficient is positive and shows that the relationship is straightforward - an increase in the enterprise number leads to an output increase. The model is adequate and statistically significant. The regression coefficient is statistically significant - $P\text{-value} < 0.05$.

$$\hat{y} = 64289 + 310,34x$$

P-value (0,6302) (0,015)
 $r = 0,5216$
 $R^2 = 0,272$
 $F = 7,0995$
Significance F = 0,0153

Figure 2 Relationship between the number of enterprises and output.

Source: Authors' calculations

The analysis shows that the correlation between the number of enterprises and the net sales revenue is significant - the correlation coefficient is $r=0.6103$ and the coefficient of determination is $R^2 = 0,3725$, which means that 37.3% of the variation in net sales revenue is due to the variation in the number of enterprises, and 66.7% of the variation is due to other factors not included in the model.

$$\hat{y} = 73939 + 390,71x$$

P-value (0,579) (0,0033)
 $r = 0,6103$
 $R^2 = 0,3725$
 $F = 11,279$
Significance F = 0,0033

Figure 9 Relationship between the number of enterprises and net sales

Source: NSI and author's calculations.

The regression coefficient is positive and shows that the relationship is straightforward - an increase in the number of enterprises leads to an increase in output. The model is adequate and statistically significant. The regression coefficient is statistically significant - $P\text{-value} < 0.05$.

Based on the study of the dependence between output and net sales revenue, it was found to be very strong - the correlation coefficient is $r=0.9639$ and the coefficient of determination is $R^2 = 0,9292$ and means

that 92.9% of the variation in net sales revenue is due to the variation in output, and 7.1% of the variation is due to the effect of other factors not included in the model. The regression coefficient is positive and shows that the relationship is straightforward - an increase in the number of enterprises leads to an increase in output. The model is adequate and statistically significant. The regression coefficient is statistically significant - $P\text{-value} < 0.05$.

$$\hat{y} = 69505 + 1,0348x$$

P-value (0,0582) (0,00000)
 $r = 0,9639$
 $R^2 = 0,9292$
 $F = 249,039$
Significance F = 0,00000

Figure 10 Relationship between output and net sales

Source: NSI and author's calculations.

Conclusion

As a result of the analysis of some key indicators of economic, social, and demographic development of the municipalities of the North-Eastern and South-Eastern regions, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Significant disparities and disproportions between the municipalities have been found, which are most pronounced in the indicators "Number of beds in accommodation", "Foreign direct investment", "Number of newly built housing units put into operation", "Number of enterprises", "Net sales revenues", "Output".

- Key factors for the differences in the development of the municipalities and determining their development potential are the territorial location, proximity to the sea opportunities for the development of tourism and all accompanying activities, the state of the local economy, the presence of traditional industries, etc.

- The indicators' analysis shows that the leading municipalities are Pomorie, Kazanlak, Balchik, Kavarna, Radnevo, and Aksakovo.

- To reduce the disparities between the municipalities of the North-Eastern and South-Eastern regions, as well as the other municipalities of the country with a population between 10,000 and 30,000 people, it is necessary to implement a special and targeted policy for priority development to increase their economic attractiveness for investors, create the needed infrastructure ensuring accessibility and connectivity, increase incomes and living standards, improve access to social infrastructure, priority funded under operational and national programs, and improve the quality of life of the municipalities.

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